

1 **Title page**

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3 **Graph theory analysis of complex brain networks: new concepts in brain mapping applied to**
4 **neurosurgery**

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1 **1. Abstract: the brain as a complex network**

2 “To make the delicate, awesome, and fateful work of the neurosurgeon more accurate, gentle and
3 safe.” This statement by Professor Al Rhoton, one of the 20th Century’s most famous neurosurgeons
4 and anatomists, encapsulates the objectives of both neurosurgical management and research.
5 Achieving this goal for many fields of neurosurgery requires preserving or improving a patient’s
6 brain function. Thus, understanding functional neuroanatomy is fundamental to the advancement of
7 surgical techniques and subsequent therapeutic strategies.

8 The human brain is the most complex system yet discovered, and understanding its form and
9 function remains as one of the greatest scientific challenges. The digital age has produced the
10 necessary technologies and concepts to begin to make sense of the bewildering complexity of this
11 most mysterious organ. Recently, ideas of the brain as a network of unceasing communication have
12 emerged by comparison to other, common, natural and manmade systems that share key
13 organizational principles ¹⁷. A combination of *in-vivo* imaging, statistical modeling, and graph
14 theoretical analysis has allowed the development of increasingly realistic models with explanatory
15 and predictive properties. A paradigm shift has subsequently arisen describing brain function as a
16 consequence of information exchange between its components rather than information processing
17 within individual components ^{83,84}.

18 Here we aim to introduce complex brain networks and graph theory to the neurosurgical community
19 (table 1). To begin, we explain how the brain can be viewed as a complex network and how graph
20 theory can be used to explore the network’s properties. With these ideas established we then
21 describe how new avenues have been created in understanding functional brain anatomy, resilience,
22 recovery, cognitive function, and disease biomarkers. Finally, we discuss how complex network
23 analyses and graph theory have already been applied to ‘real world’ scenarios including traumatic
24 brain injury, neuro-oncology, and functional neurosurgery for psychiatric disease.

25

1 **2. Development of the network based approach: a historical perspective**

2 Non-invasive, tomographic, *in-vivo* functional neuroimaging began with the discovery of Blood
3 Oxygenation-Level Dependent (BOLD) endogenous contrast⁶⁸ where neuronal activity produces
4 local blood oxygenation changes detectable by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). The cognitive
5 neuroscience community was an early adopter of this technology with a burgeoning in discoveries
6 that certain brain functions are localized to anatomical regions, previously only surmised through
7 lesioning studies or electrophysiological studies{Varela:2001bs} (with significant contributions
8 from neurosurgery{Greenblatt:1997uf}). . However, it was soon discovered, using positron emission
9 tomography (PET), that task-induced activity accounts for only 1-5% of the total energy budget of
10 the brain, the most energetically expensive human organ. The great majority of brain metabolism is
11 consumed continually, even in the absence of a cognitive stimulus⁷¹ when it is at “rest”.

12 Changing the focus from task-based experiments to analyzing spontaneous activity while
13 participants were resting revealed synchronous low frequency (<0.1Hz) fluctuations in the BOLD
14 signal that formed coherent networks of neural activity¹³. Central to this frame-shift in thinking was
15 the discovery of the so-called default mode network (DMN), a synchronous set of dispersed brain
16 regions continuously active at rest, but reduced in activity during cognitively effortful tasks^{37,90}.
17 The close relationship of the DMN, and other resting state networks, to task based activation
18 patterns⁸⁰ implies an interconnectedness between brain networks and the underlying structural
19 connectivity^{26,46}.

20 Describing the organizational characteristics and evolution of networks in both space and time has
21 been the subject of many mathematical approaches (for example dynamic casual modeling
22 (DCM)¹¹, independent component analysis (ICA)¹¹, and graph theory¹⁷). While a network approach
23 to brain function is not a new idea{Sporns:2012uz, Sporns:tk}{Hebb:1942je, Catani:2005dt,
24 Mesulam:1990cn}, recent focus on brain connectivity as the underlying principle of the brain has
25 gained eminence in the past decade, culminating in the search for the connectome, or the brains
26 ‘wiring diagram’{Sporns:2005ki}. Synonymous with this rise in networks and connectomics has
27 been the emergence of resting functional (F)MRI, although important contributions have come from
28 a variety of neuroimaging modalities (table 2) including: EEG⁶⁵; MEG⁸⁵; PET^{29,75}; structural
29 MRI⁴⁵; and diffusion based imaging^{42,43}. In short, there is now a large movement in neuroimaging
30 studies towards viewing the functional integration or connectivity, superseding functional
31 segregation and the localizationist viewpoint³⁹. **3. What is a complex network?**

1 Graph theory was originally devised to solve real world problems by viewing the system as an
2 abstract network (figure 1), which then allowed its properties to be analyzed mathematically ³⁶. A
3 network consists of point-like components, nodes or vertices, V , and the relationships between
4 them, links or edges, E . For example, when characterizing social relationships nodes are individual
5 people and the presence or absence of an edge between two nodes indicates whether the
6 corresponding people are friends or not. Together, the sets of nodes and edges form a binary
7 ‘friendship’ graph: $G=\{V,E\}$. Further information can be encoded, for example the strength of the
8 friendship can be represented by assigning a value, or weight to the edges. Weighted or binary
9 graphs can be directed, if an edge has an associated direction, say if each person were independently
10 asked about their relationships with others in the network, or undirected in which case no
11 directionality in the relationships is implied.

12 The strength of graph theory is that once a graph has been constructed, the specific meanings of the
13 nodes and edges becomes irrelevant, and the same analyses can therefore be applied to graphs
14 originating from a wide spectrum of real-world networks.

15 *Network measures*

16 Once the graph is formed, the properties of it (and therefore the real-life network it represents) can
17 be captured in mathematically (figure 2). In a binary graph the simplest property is the degree of a
18 node, the number of connections or links that it has, which is a measure of how well the node is
19 connected. The degree distribution is the histogram of node degrees for the overall network and is
20 an important network property ⁵ that can be used to distinguish between networks (described
21 below). The total number of connections in a network can also be regarded as an estimate of the
22 *cost* in establishing a particular configuration ².

23 Two network concepts of particular interest are segregation and integration ⁸⁹. Network segregation
24 relates to how well the network can be separated into constituent communities of nodes. A standard
25 measure for determining segregation is clustering, which can be thought of as the tendency of nodes
26 that share neighbors to be connected (e.g. are your friends each other’s friends?).

27 Network integration measures the connectedness of distinct regions. One way of defining this is by
28 the number of edges required to move from any one node to a target node, and when taken as an
29 average across all nodes in the network is known as the average path length ⁹⁸. A related measure is
30 global efficiency, which is the inverse of path length ⁵⁶, but which has a greater relative contribution
31 from short-distance connections ². Note that these metrics are restricted to topological connections
32 and don’t take into account geometrical distance between nodes.

1 *Network models*

2 An alternative to computing a network's metrics, which are mainly descriptive, is to propose
3 models of graph structure that explain the measured properties³. Historically, two simple models,
4 amenable to mathematical analysis, have been studied (figure 3). A lattice graph is a regular array
5 of nodes with connections solely between adjacent nodes. As all connections are local, lattices show
6 a high clustering coefficient, but also a high path length (as getting from one edge of the graph to
7 another requires traversing a large number of nodes). Another extreme is formed by the random
8 graph, where nodes are connected at random. As this leads to few local connections, random graphs
9 have low clustering, but short path lengths. Neither lattices nor random graphs represent accurate
10 models of real world networks.

11 Graph theory experienced a quantum leap in the late 1990s when two seminal papers showed a
12 range of real world networks were well approximated by two simple network models. The first of
13 these created graphs by 're-wiring' lattices: converting some of the short range connections into
14 long range connections⁹⁸. It was found that after only a few re-wirings the graphs showed a
15 strongly reduced average path length, while maintaining high clustering. This property, where most
16 interactions are local (high segregation) but it is still possible to reach any part of the graph in a few
17 steps (high integration), was dubbed the 'small world' property. It was found to be ubiquitous, with
18 examples including the Internet, Hollywood actor collaborations, power grid organization, and
19 neural networks.

20 Concurrent with the formulation of small world networks, another feature found to be common in
21 many real world networks is the existence of a small number of highly connected nodes (called
22 'hubs')⁶. This network model could be generated using a simple process of sequentially adding
23 nodes to a graph and preferentially attaching them to nodes that already had many connections (e.g.
24 everyone wants to be friends with the popular person). The resulting degree distribution follows a
25 power law. Many real world networks have been found to exhibit this property, although often the
26 distribution is capped due to physical restraints (e.g. the finite size of a brain), in which case an
27 exponentially truncated power law degree distribution is appropriate¹.

28 Since the 1990s, small world networks and scale-free degree distributions have been the defining
29 properties of complex networks with non-trivial topological features, contrasting with random
30 graphs and lattices. Conservation of network properties over a wide range of fields has facilitated
31 trans-disciplinary sharing of rules for growth, evolution, and robustness between networks. The
32 realization that these rules could model the behavior of real networks has led to the establishment

1 and blossoming of network science over the past two decades and the application of complex
2 networks to the central nervous systems of vertebrates and invertebrates, including humans.

3

1 **4. How are brain networks abstracted from empirical data?**

2 Methods of constructing graphs from diverse neuroimaging modalities share many similar concepts
3 (figure 4), but with subtle differences that depend on the nature of the data ^{17,36}. Multiple spatial
4 scales of data can be accommodated ranging from micro-scales (e.g. light microscopy and
5 cytoarchitecture, typically ~10 μm) through meso-scales (e.g. viral tracers, typically ~0.1 mm) to
6 macro-scales (e.g. MRI, typically ~1 mm) ⁸⁴. Whatever data input and planned inferences are
7 chosen subsequently defines the consequent network as either: structural, if anatomical data is used
8 (e.g. diffusion imaging or cortical morphology); functional, if temporally varying data is the basis
9 (e.g. resting FMRI, EEG, MEG, or PET); or effective, if the data is attempting to suggest causal
10 influences between regions (i.e. a directed graph).

11 Recalling that both vertices and edges are required to construct a network, the first stage is to define
12 the nodes. This may be straightforward, for example the positions of EEG or MEG electrodes, or
13 require division of tomographic brain imaging data by some arbitrary, although principled method,
14 known as parcellation. ¹⁰².

15 Once nodes have been established, edges have to be defined. For data collected over time, such as
16 EEG, MEG or resting FMRI, the strength of a connection between two nodes is frequently
17 estimated by the Pearson's correlation between their time-series, although other methods can also
18 be used¹⁰¹. For data without temporal information such as estimates of brain structure from MRI
19 (cortical thickness, grey matter volume, and cortical surface), edge strengths are the covariance of
20 observations between-individuals and thus represent the average connections within a group or
21 population sample ⁴⁵. Diffusion MRI uses a slightly different method whereby the number of tracts
22 (calculated from a tractography algorithm) are calculated between parcels ^{42,43}.

23 Once these calculations are complete the data are organized into a two-dimensional adjacency
24 matrix, where nodes are represented by rows and columns, and edge weights are indicated by the
25 matrix entries, as each entry lies at the intersection of a row and column. After= this point the
26 methods of analysis are shared irrespective of the original data or the final objective of the analysis
27 ⁵¹. Once the graph has been created its properties can be characterized using a range of graph theory
28 measures. Toolboxes have been developed with optimized coding to provide efficient, reliable, and
29 standardized computation of measures and methods for statistical testing ⁷³.

30 One of the most appealing aspects of networks is their representation or visualization that renders
31 them in a manner which makes interpretation possible ⁶². However, currently there is no
32 standardized way in which to do this, and the choice of technique depends on the data and planned

1 inferences (figure 5). Traditionally, visualizing neuroimaging data, particularly that for task FMRI,
2 has emphasized anatomical accuracy and clarity. However, for connectivity and graph theory
3 analyses, the emphasis changes to the pattern of interactions between any two nodes.

4

5

1 **5. The brain's small world - new insights from graph theory into anatomical models**

2 A fundamental property of brain networks – either structural or functional – is that they demonstrate
3 clear small world characteristics; that is, they are simultaneously segregated (high clustering
4 coefficient) and integrated (short path lengths) ^{10,81,98}. In this manner they parsimoniously balance
5 the needs of localized specialization and global efficiency. This highly non-random pattern of
6 connections is also remarkably sparse, in that the overall number of binary connections is a small
7 proportion (~5-10%) of the maximum number possible, emphasizing the highly organized nature of
8 brain networks ¹⁰⁰. Small world characteristics and sparse networks are complimentary features in
9 that they demonstrate how simultaneous segregation and integration can be achieved at a low cost
10 of connections. Sparse small world attributes are robust in that they are reproducible across imaging
11 modalities (diffusion MRI ^{42,43}, resting fMRI ^{1,74,97}, structural MRI ⁴⁵, EEG⁷⁸, MEG⁸⁵, and
12 PET^{29,75}), disease states, and species (such as the cat, macaque, and nematode *caenorhabditis*
13 *elegans*)¹⁹.

14 The degree distribution of brain networks is difficult to accurately reproduce due to the small
15 number of overall connections using common parcellations ⁵². However, it appears that brain
16 networks do not demonstrate scale-free properties in their degree distribution, but rather have an
17 exponentially truncated power law ¹. This is not entirely unexpected given the space constraints
18 involved. In other words, it would be difficult to imagine having sufficient room for a brain growing
19 inside a closed space like the skull to accommodate super-connected regions that would reside in
20 the extreme tail of the degree distribution ⁵. Other topologically constrained networks such as
21 transportation networks and internet routers face similar issues ⁶.

22 Highly connected nodes have been identified through a variety of means ^{7,38} that quantify how
23 central these nodes are in the network ⁹¹. These hubs are believed to a key role in facilitating the
24 flow of information in the network, but it is unlikely that they are eloquent *per se*. Furthermore, the
25 distribution of connections between such hubs is often found to be significantly non-random, with
26 highly connected hubs even more strongly connected to each other in a so-called 'rich club' ⁹².

27 Community detection is performed by grouping nodes into communities or modules such that they
28 are more strongly connected to nodes within their own module than to those in other modules ⁶⁷.
29 Modules derived from a graph theoretical treatment are consistent with those identified using other
30 means of assessing brain connectivity ⁹⁰. These modules can be further broken down into sub-
31 modules in a hierarchical manner ⁷⁴ Within these modules, highly connected hubs have been
32 identified which are further sub-classified as either connector hubs if they link modules, or

1 provincial hubs if they mainly integrate nodes within a module ^{41,82}. Modularity reflects local
2 specialization, but also allows cost effective network integration by adding a few long-range
3 connections between modules.

4 Rules for neural network growth have been developed that try to accurately predict the behavior of
5 real networks. For instance, when new nodes are connected preferentially to a highly connected
6 ‘rich club’, the degree distribution matches that of other real world networks, a scenario known as
7 the ‘rich get richer’ ⁶. Other models include the ageing of vertices, whereby a certain number of
8 nodes disappears over time, a process that replicates scale-free degree distributions ⁵. Clarifying the
9 constraints and stimuli for network growth may allow insights into brain repair or adaptation after
10 injury.

11 It should now be apparent that network models of brain structure and function aim to describe how
12 the simultaneous demands of functional segregation and integration are met. In this new
13 perspective, the focus changes from a localization approach, in which particular cognitive functions
14 takes place in specified brain regions, to an integrative or connectomics based approach that
15 emphasizes information flow across the entire network. Additionally, the vocabulary that
16 accompanies graph theory offers a new way of expressing the exploration of the brain. A prominent
17 structural and functional core can be defined based on specific hubs, modules, and efficiency, which
18 can be used to re-explore classical models of brain activity. Whether differences in network
19 parameters can be identified with enough reliability to encompass individual variability, dynamic
20 reconfiguration, and evolutionary changes remains to be seen.

21

22

1 **6. Applications of graph theory in neurosurgery: a new concept in brain mapping**

2 While graph theory analysis of complex networks has allowed significant advances in our
3 understanding of normal brain structure and function, to be clinically relevant it must also make
4 neurosurgery “more accurate, gentle, and safe”. We now discuss how graph theory can be applied to
5 brain mapping, and in doing so give a new perspective that sees function from a connectivity-based
6 perspective, rather purely localized. Supplementing traditional methods of brain mapping (such as
7 intra-operative cortical stimulation), graph theory also allows prediction of dynamic changes
8 (possibly in a reparative manner), as well predicting how the brain can adapt, or not, to the presence
9 of focal lesions, including those purposefully induced by surgery.

10 **6a. Understanding function**

11 Graph theory has characterized brain functional organization as a highly efficient, small world
12 network. Understanding how this network architecture affects intellectual function may enable the
13 abstract concepts and measures of graph theory to develop clinically relevant meaning. For
14 example, certain network features may reflect the capacity of an individual to perform a specific
15 neurocognitive task.

16 To understand the relationship between function and individual networks, comparison with
17 statistical techniques such as ICA have been particularly insightful. Networks identified through
18 ICA of fMRI data in the absence of an external stimulus were compared spatially to those derived
19 during experiments that required cognitive engagement⁸⁰. A close correspondence was found
20 between behavioral domains in the corresponding task-based fMRI and resting fMRI networks,
21 suggesting at baseline the brain is already organized along functional boundaries. It can then be
22 hypothesized that such modules (and hierarchical sub-modules) represent a repertoire of functional
23 networks that can be called upon for task-directed activities.

24 Experiments examining intelligence and network topology found a higher intelligence quotient (IQ)
25 was negatively correlated with path length but not with clustering or overall connectivity⁹³. As a
26 longer path length is inversely proportional to efficiency, this suggests that network efficiency is a
27 key factor for cognitive function. Furthermore, the medial prefrontal cortex and precuneus (among
28 other regions) were identified as having the greatest effect on network organization and global
29 network efficiency. Notably, this study is a demonstration of how task performance patterns are
30 reflected in functional connectivity at rest.

1 This critical role of path length and its inverse, efficiency, has been corroborated in a study
2 examining brain structural networks⁵⁹. High intelligence corresponds to higher global efficiency in
3 both weighted and binary graphs. During the performance of a task, a more prominent small world
4 architecture was found in those without higher education than in those with a University education,
5 suggesting that more efficient network communication was required in the former group in order to
6 complete the task⁶⁵. Thus, efficiency appears to be the key determinant of intellectual function.
7 Relating network topology to specific neuropsychological tasks and to the effects of cortical
8 stimulation findings will be critical to translating graph theoretical measures to clinically
9 meaningful phenotypes.

10 **6b. Characterizing plasticity**

11 Brain networks are not static, but are dynamic over a wide range of time scales: from seconds to
12 years. Normal development offers an ideal opportunity to measure the long-term evolution of their
13 properties. In terms of neurosurgical relevance, characteristic patterns of network dynamics could
14 be used as a proxy for plasticity and to explain recovery from focal neurological disorders.

15

16 Development of a single specific brain network, the default mode network (DMN), has been studied
17 in a cohort of children aged 7-9 years comparing to adults aged 21-31 years^{33,34}. In children, the
18 DMN was sparsely connected and tended to follow anatomical (or local) patterns in their
19 connections, whereas in adults, the DMN had developed into a more densely connected network
20 encompassing the characteristic DMN regions. An earlier analysis of the same data found that
21 developmental connectivity was characterized by an increase in long-range connections and
22 decrease in short-range connections with increasing age, suggesting that as the graphs became less
23 sparse, connections also changed from being anatomically to functionally coupled³⁴.

24 Refinement of connections and the role of path length was investigated in a whole-brain network
25 model using combined structural and functional imaging data⁸⁸. With increasing age there was a
26 reduction of short-range connections and increase in long-range connectivity. This is analogous to
27 processes occurring at cellular scales where over-connectivity is refined through selective pruning.
28 By adulthood networks had also developed an increased hierarchy and the inter-regional
29 connectivity patterns had changed to form stronger cortico-cortical, but weaker subcortical-cortical
30 connections.

1 Characteristic patterns of development have allowed machine learning algorithms to predict brain
2 maturation patterns with 92% accuracy³⁰. Weakening of short-range functional connections
3 between major brain functional modules was the most important factor in the model, confirming the
4 importance of connection pruning to overall development. Other changes over time identified
5 included strengthening of long-range connections, increased segregation and modularity. Overall
6 this produced modules that were more segregated from each other, but more densely connected
7 within themselves.

8 These findings suggest that networks demonstrate characteristic patterns of dynamics over the two
9 or more decades of brain development, converging to a more cohesive, efficient, and modular
10 topology^{28,58}. Network models of development appear complimentary to traditional models, for
11 example Hebbian learning, whereby repeated stimulation of one cell by another leads to increased
12 synaptic efficiency⁹⁵. Determining the rules behind these network dynamics will require
13 understanding of how they relate to neuro-cognitive traits, learning, and evolution.

14 From a neurosurgical perspective, lesions (either pathological or surgically induced) could trigger
15 mechanisms that normally occur during development in order to repair the network. Using these
16 principles, a description of how a brain network reconnects following attenuation or removal of
17 specific nodes and edges could lead to an explanation of adaptation and reconstituted function.
18 Potentially rehabilitation could be tailored to the expected dynamic cascade of effects, or lack
19 thereof.

20 **6c. Modeling the effects of lesions**

21 Analysis of the effects of lesions on brain function has a long tradition of providing insights into
22 functional localization⁷², which has been complimented by high-resolution neuroimaging⁹⁶.
23 However, understanding brain function from a localization perspective fails to account for dynamic
24 changes, individual variability, and neurocognitive processes that require distributed rather than
25 discrete processing. Network based analysis of lesion effects offers a complimentary consideration
26 of system-wide functional disturbance. In addition, models can be readily created to virtually
27 examine the effects of postulated lesions.

28 Network models can be computationally “lesioned” by either randomly removing nodes (‘random
29 error’) or targeting removal of certain nodes based on their specific parameters, e.g. removing
30 highly central hubs (‘targeted attack’). The robustness of the network can be calculated by
31 comparing the topology after lesioning with the prior, intact network. An exponentially truncated
32 power law degree distribution has been found to confer robustness to random error, but also leaves

1 the network vulnerable to specific removal of hubs¹. Rather than brain development selecting for
2 such robustness, it is more likely that it is a by-product of the formation of developing efficient
3 processing through a rich-club organizational topology⁵².

4 Modeling the effect of larger, potentially more realistic lesions was performed on a structural
5 connectivity data set with simulated neural dynamics⁴. Structural networks were robust to random
6 node deletion or targeted removal of nodes based on their degree or strength, but vulnerable to
7 targeted removal of highly central ‘hub’ nodes. Simulated dynamic effects of lesions varied in size
8 and spatial pattern depending on the lesion location, with lesions in the midline as well as those
9 involving temporo-parietal junction and superior frontal gyrus tending to have the greatest effect on
10 neural dynamics. In general, lesions reduced functional connectivity, with effects most pronounced
11 in the ipsilateral hemisphere, but also extending in a non-local manner to the contra-lateral
12 hemisphere. Finally, the extent that alterations of the structural network produced dynamic
13 consequences was most accurately predicted by injury to the DMN rather than, for instance, the
14 degree or strength of connections directly incorporated by the lesion. How these simulated lesions
15 and corresponding network disruption relate to actual neuropsychological findings in patients is
16 awaiting confirmation. However, it is likely that the relationship between simulated and *in-vivo*
17 lesions is considerably more complex and includes dynamic reparative mechanisms.

18 White matter or structural disconnectivity and its effects on function networks have been studied in
19 a model of structural networks created from empirical data followed by a computer simulation of
20 resting-state BOLD signals using the network as a substrate. Randomly removing links or
21 decreasing the global coupling strength resulted in characteristic patterns of increased hierarchy,
22 efficiency, and robustness, but reduced small worldness, clustering and generated a narrower degree
23 distribution²⁰. This pattern of altered network dynamics was found to be similar to that found in
24 patients with schizophrenia, suggesting that altered structural connectivity could be responsible for
25 dynamic and phenotypic changes. However, the effects of focal lesions are unlikely to be explained
26 purely in terms of alterations to structural connectivity, and will most likely require a model
27 combining structural and functional factors.

28 A network approach has revealed key features in terms of the robustness and resilience to lesioning
29 of the brain. Application of theory from other complex systems in response, for example, to the re-
30 routing of traffic after road closures^{25,27}, or percolation theory and the degree to which networks
31 can be impaired (‘slowed down’) before critical function is affected (as opposed to directly
32 removing a node)²² offer potential to understanding the subtleties of changes in information flow
33 due to lesions. Network models of lesion effects could also be elaborated to encompass dynamic

1 changes and potential neurocognitive functional consequences. Cognitive deficits could then be
2 predicted based on the vulnerability of a network to attack and its potential for repair.

3 More speculatively, accurate lesion modeling could be utilized in intra-operative brain mapping to
4 define the extent of resection or the effects of a surgical intervention. One can envision classifying
5 brain regions into those that are highly vulnerable, sub serve critical function, or have limited
6 potential for recovery, and thus need to be preserved. On the other hand, regions may be highly
7 resilient, have limited functional importance, or have significant dynamic potential for re-
8 organization. In this case a safer resection could be predicted with little functional consequence.

9

1 **7. Review of current and potential applications of graph theory in neurosurgery**

2 **7a. Traumatic brain injury**

3 Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is a heterogeneous condition encompassing a wide range of
4 pathologies and potential outcomes. Network based approaches offer potential to increase our
5 understanding of disease pathophysiology, mechanisms underlying neurocognitive deficits, and the
6 progress and effects of rehabilitation.

7 Defining patterns of injury based on functional connectivity could provide biomarkers to aid in
8 differential diagnosis and prognosis with greater validity than can be obtained from radiological
9 assessment of standard clinical MRI sequences. In a study of patients with mild TBI, networks had
10 a longer average path length, reduced overall cost and reduced network efficiency compared to
11 controls⁶⁹. In addition, TBI characteristically produced injury focused on the posterior cingulate
12 cortex, known to be a critical hub in the normally functioning brain. Increasing the validity of these
13 measures may allow individual prediction of a given injury's effect on the network as well as
14 identification of characteristic disease 'fingerprints' corresponding to specific pathologies.

15 Assessing TBI in terms of network dysfunction has allowed re-appraisal of pathologies that have
16 previously proven enigmatic. For example, blast related head injuries are a relatively recent
17 phenomena characterized by minimal abnormalities on standard structural MRI⁴⁴. However,
18 network measures are grossly deranged, with higher modularity and lower average participation
19 coefficient in patients. Thus, certain injuries could be defined solely in terms of their functional
20 connectivity.

21 Subtle cognitive deficits that have significant functional impairment are now being appreciated
22 clinically even after minor head injury and concussion. Mechanisms of cognitive deficits after head
23 injury have been investigated using graph theory measures. In a study of adults with minor TBI, the
24 function of a given network was compared to that of healthy controls in a task-switching cognitive
25 challenge²¹. Task performance was significantly poorer in patients than in controls. Patients had
26 increased connectivity and local efficiency compared to controls, both of which were correlated
27 with task proficiency and severity of TBI. It is proposed that these connectivity markers reflect
28 network reorganization in an attempt to compensate for the injury.

29 Rehabilitation after TBI is now being given increased clinical priority, but exactly how to tailor and
30 assess the effectiveness of such therapy is contentious. Reorganization of functional networks
31 during neurorehabilitation found baseline measurements soon after injury replicated known patterns

1 of network disruption including increased path length and increased connectivity, during recovery,
2 these measures were restored to normal levels ²³. Recovery of network measures also correlated
3 positively with neurocognitive recovery, enhancing their validity and providing clinical meaning.
4 This opens up the possibility that network measures could be a sensitive and objective means of
5 monitoring recovery.

6 Finally, a connectomics approach has been used to cast new light on the notable example of head
7 injury suffered by Phineas Gage⁹⁴. A simulated trajectory of the iron bar was overlaid on a
8 structural connectome from a healthy volunteer to model the extent of injury on grey and white
9 matter. While this indeed confirmed notable local injury it also identified patterns of widespread
10 and long-range connectivity loss that could also have contributed to the characteristic post-injury
11 behavioral patterns described.

12 Potential future avenues for network analysis and graph theory in TBI are extensive ⁷⁷. Injuries that
13 do not have significant associated structural changes (i.e. without focal injury such as hematomas or
14 contusions) are ideal for graph theory analysis as they simplify pre-processing of the data and
15 comparison with example networks. Models of lesion effects that encompass brain function,
16 plasticity, and resilience could be adapted to guide rehabilitation programs. Biomarkers based on
17 network measures could have multiple applications in clinical trials, for example in selecting
18 homogenous trial populations based on graph theory characteristics, or in objective means of
19 assessing the effects of cognitive enhancing medications.

20

21 **7b. Deep Brain Stimulation for neuropsychiatric conditions**

22 A disconnectivity hypothesis has been proposed to explain certain neurological and psychiatric
23 diseases ^{17,24}. Aberrant connectivity of a structural or functional network (for example in terms of
24 impaired network integration or segregation) is proposed to lead to the development of clinical
25 symptoms. Deep brain stimulation (DBS) has been used for psychiatric conditions, but its
26 mechanism of action is poorly understood and the effects capricious ⁵⁴.

27 Defining psychiatric diseases partly based on network parameters allows the effectiveness of DBS
28 to be assessed in terms of how it is able to reset functional connectivity to within the normal range.
29 In patients with obsessive compulsive disorder, DBS of the nucleus accumbens normalized
30 frontostriatal connectivity from excessive levels ³⁵. A positive correlation between symptomatic

1 relief and reduction in excess frontostriatal connectivity was found, implying that restoring network
2 activity is an important objective for effective treatment.

3 Other psychiatric diseases that have been modeled with graph theory and which are of potential
4 relevance for deep brain stimulation include depression and post-traumatic stress disorder. In
5 depression, connectivity within the default mode network and fronto-thalamo-caudate regions was
6 reduced⁵³, community structure was rearranged⁶¹, and hubs were altered⁶⁰. Furthermore, depressed
7 patients and healthy controls could be automatically classified with multivariate pattern analysis
8 (94% accuracy) ¹⁰³ and support vector machines (99% accuracy)⁶¹. If these network configurations
9 prove to be robust biomarkers, they could be used to stratify patients into homogenous groups in
10 clinical trials or indeed as selection criteria in themselves.

11 Network based outcome assessment has also been applied in a study of DBS of the periventricular /
12 periaqueductal grey (PVG/PAG) for chronic phantom limb pain ⁵⁵. During stimulation, subjective
13 symptom relief was correlated with significantly increased activity in the left mid-anterior
14 orbitofrontal cortex and right subgenus cingulate cortex, both of which are known to be involved in
15 pain relief. Moreover, when the stimulator was turned off, worsening symptoms were associated
16 with reduced activity in the same areas, and yielding a robust and reproducible effect of stimulation.

17 Combining functional connectivity analysis and the effects of DBS can also improve our
18 understanding of disease pathophysiology, particularly when there is a lack of realistic animal
19 models, such as for chronic pain. DBS of the anterior cingulate cortex in chronic pain produced
20 stimulation-specific relief of symptoms that was accompanied by diffuse functional connectivity
21 changes in the pre-supplementary motor area, brainstem peri-aqueductal gray matter, rostral
22 anterior cingulate, and medial prefrontal areas ⁶⁶. As well as depicting the widespread networks
23 involved in chronic pain, this study also improves understanding of the effects of stimulating the
24 anterior cingulate cortex, which can be an effective DBS target for a range of conditions including
25 depression and obsessive-compulsive disorder.

26 Further studies combining DBS and complex network analyses may allow individual tailoring of
27 therapy based on features of the abnormal network. For example, the specific manner in which a
28 network is perturbed in depression may vary between individuals, and this could be used to identify
29 an individualized target for stimulation. Refinement of graph theory biomarkers could potentially
30 aid titration of stimulation parameters that optimize network reconfiguration.

31

1 **7c. Neuro-oncology**

2 A fundamental goal in the resection of intrinsic brain lesions is to maximize the extent of resection
3 for oncological gain^{86,87} while preserving brain function⁶³ and ensuring a good quality of life.
4 Current surgical methods in neuro-oncology including awake surgery⁷⁶, cortical mapping²⁷, and
5 neurophysiological techniques¹², have led to significant advancements in patient outcome and the
6 emergence of supra-marginal resections whereby tumor resections are extended to functional
7 boundaries⁵⁰. Brain mapping has played a key role in the field since the pioneering days of Penfield
8⁷⁰ and identification of the sensory-motor homunculus, while more recent studies have suggested a
9 hierarchical topology is involved in restoring function after lesions³². Network science and graph
10 theory represents a new language with which to progress our understanding.

11 An abnormal signature of brain connectivity has been identified in patients with brain tumors^{8,9,99}.
12 In general, brain networks in patients with tumours have been found to be more random and less
13 organized, not just locally but in a diffuse manner. Specific findings include reduced efficiency in
14 patients with tumours in the frontal and temporal but not parietal lobes. Also, network hubs were
15 also re-organized, with the right insula being a hub in controls but not patients. A follow-up study
16 focusing on frontal lobe tumour confirmed reduced local efficiency but increased global efficiency,
17 and reduced clustering⁴⁷. Whether these global network dynamics reflect compensatory
18 mechanisms or possible non-local effects of the tumor is awaiting clarification.

19 For graph theory measures to have clinical relevance it is necessary to relate network disruption to
20 the patient's symptoms and function. The degree to which network features are perturbed has been
21 correlated with neuropsychological deficits involving both local and diffuse brain regions with
22 reduced global efficiency, and small worldness correlated with lower IQ scores^{14,15,99}. Applying
23 graph theory measures to identify the neuropsychological function of a network allows a novel
24 means to map out a functional resection boundary depending on the anticipated cognitive
25 consequences.

26 Surgical effects on networks and how this corresponds to clinical outcomes has been measured^{40,47}.
27 Networks have been found to be restored to a more organized state post-surgery from a more
28 disorganized state pre-operatively. Additionally, a specific pattern of network disruption pre-
29 operatively was able to predict whether neurocognitive outcome⁴⁰. Regions that showed decreased
30 coherence could be resected without new deficits appearing, while increased connectivity was
31 associated with eloquent tissue. Seizure outcome has also been correlated with improvement in
32 network characteristics³¹. In this case there was a trend for patients without seizures to have a

1 larger decrease in inter-hemispheric connectivity in the theta band. Modeling the effects of surgery
2 and the predicted network effects may thus offer a new avenue in pre-operative surgical planning.
3 For example, surgery could be tailored to produce a predicted network effect that prevents new
4 neuropsychological deficits or optimizes seizure outcome.

5 These preliminary studies demonstrate the potential of using network measures to assess clinical
6 function and the effects of surgery in patients with brain tumors. Modeling the effects of lesions
7 (and surgery) on networks offers a way to analyze the predicted effects of surgery on a network
8 which in turn could be used to tailor the extent of resection based on the anticipated functional
9 consequences and potential for network re-organization. This final concept will involve unification
10 of concepts of brain function, plasticity (re-connectomics), and network vulnerability.

11

12

1 **8. Conclusions**

2 Complex network analysis and graph theory offer new horizons for exploring the effects of focal
3 and diffuse pathologies managed in neurosurgery. Although the field is relatively new, its trans-
4 disciplinary nature means it has developed on validated concepts from associated areas such as the
5 social sciences and communication engineering. Already our understanding of neuropsychiatric
6 conditions has advanced through applying these techniques, but so far applications within
7 neurosurgery have been relatively rare. Specific roles for network science in neurosurgery include
8 mapping brain function, characterizing plasticity, and modeling brain robustness.

9 Ultimately though the challenge will be to apply this understanding to patients to enhance clinical
10 improvement of their management ^{18,57}. Part of the translational efficacy will lie with improved
11 technical standards in creating graphs to make them more credible, reliable, and intuitive ⁷⁹. For
12 instance, developing fully connected weighted graphs without arbitrary thresholding, or developing
13 realistic null models to benchmark network characteristics. Once this is in place applying a network
14 analysis to standard clinical MRI scans could feasibly become routine. However the most attractive
15 opportunity is probably in integrating realistic models of brain lesions (factoring in function,
16 plasticity, and robustness) to pre-operative planning and neuronavigation as integral to surgical
17 planning. Basic science research into functional brain mapping has aligned itself along a path that
18 considers the brain as a product of its connections rather than isolated functional locations:
19 integrating these advancements into clinical brain mapping will therefore be at the forefront of
20 making neurosurgery “more accurate, gentle, and safe”.

21

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23

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Figure legends

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8 **Figure 1:** The Königsberg bridge problem

9 The city of Königsberg in Prussia (now Kaliningrad in Russia) was set of the river Pregel
10 incorporating several islands connected by seven bridges. The problem involved was finding a way
11 to walk through the city such that every bridge would be crossed once and only once. In 1735,
12 Leonard Euler (1707-1783) mapped the problem out in terms of a simple graph, which allowed him
13 to analyze the problem with mathematical rigor and generate a formal proof. It was shown that there
14 was no solution, as for it to be true the graph needed less than two nodes of odd degree. The general
15 term for traversing a network by passing each edge once and only once is now termed an 'Eulerian
16 walk'.

1

2 **Figure 2:** Network measures.

3 The main network measures and their classification are summarized in a hypothetical network
 4 illustration. Measures of segregation focus on community structure either in the form of small
 5 triangles (clustering) or larger groups of related components (modules). Measures of integration are
 6 based on the number of steps (edges) between individual nodes (known as the path length). The
 7 final main class of network measures are hubs, which can be defined in a variety of ways,
 8 depending either on how many links they have (degree), or how many paths.

9

10 **Figure 3:** Network types and the “small world”

11 The two traditional classes of network models (lattice and random graphs) are shown on either end
 12 of a spectrum with small world graphs lying in the middle. By re-wiring a few of the short range
 13 connections in the lattice to any other node with a fixed probability, the small world graph

1 maintains high clustering (a key feature of the lattice) but dramatically reduces its path length (in
 2 keeping with a random graph), thereby parsimoniously balancing the features of segregation and
 3 integration. When the lattice has become completely rewired randomly, it has become a random
 4 graph.

5

6 **Figure 4:** Constructing a graph from resting FMRI data

7 Firstly, the brain is parcellated into discrete regions (or nodes). In this case, a random parcellation is
 8 chosen based on an anatomical atlas but keeping the surface area constant. Subsequently, the mean
 9 time series of the 4D resting FMRI data is extracted for each parcel, and the relationship between
 10 each pair of these is calculated (known as an edge, or a link). Usually this relationship is the
 11 Pearson correlation, although it can also be other measures, but it is essentially a form of statistical
 12 dependency. Once this has been done for each pair of parcels, the data is displayed in terms of an
 13 adjacency matrix that highlights the connectivity between each region. In the matrix, rows and
 14 columns represent parcels (or nodes), and the relationships (or edges) are the entries in the matrix.
 15 The matrix can then be thresholded, binarized, or arranged in a hierarchical fashion. Finally, the
 16 connectivity data is translated back into anatomical space for display purpose. In this case it is
 17 overlaid with a translucent brain with lines to reflect significant links between regions, and the
 18 colors represent the module that the node belongs to.

1

2 **Figure 5:** Network visualization

3 In the simplest form, connectivity data can be represented in terms of a two-dimensional adjacency
 4 matrix, although this does not take into account any spatial information. Translating connectivity
 5 patterns to physical space was originally performed in a two-dimensional plane (A) where lines
 6 were used to denote connections between regions in physical space ^{1,74}. A weakness of this
 7 approach was that it often wasn't reconcilable with recognizable anatomy, a concern that can be
 8 allayed by rendering the wiring diagram on a surface reconstruction (B). A limitation of displaying
 9 heavily connected and detailed graphs is line clutter, whereby the graph appears to represent a
 10 lattice, and extracting information from the figure becomes impractical. Techniques borrowed from
 11 other complex network displays such as hierarchical edge bundling ¹⁶ can be used to clarify the
 12 display of such information, although with the caveat that this can risk interpreting edges in brain
 13 networks as actual white matter tracts (C). If the function of individual nodes is of interest, varying
 14 node size or color can help illustrate their properties without requiring edges to be displayed (D).
 15 This can be of use when characterizing hubs and their associated 'rich clubs' for example. Finally,
 16 more abstract renditions of connectivity data can be performed, whereby the display is detached
 17 almost completely from traditional anatomical localization, and instead emphasizes complexity and
 18 multivariate display of data (E) ^{48,49,64}. Movie representations have also been proposed to
 19 demonstrate dynamics in graph evolution.